

LANGUAGE CHANGE: DIFFERENT FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE IT

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***Abstract:** Change is inevitable, so is in the case of language. Languages change over time. It can be at any level of structure- phonological, morphological, syntax, semantics and lexical. Changes are gradual and also may vary at different levels. Phonemes, morphemes, words and even rules of languages may be added, altered or even lost. The lexicon of a language may be broadened by the presence of borrowing words and loan words.*

***Key words:** Change, symbol, structure, Language, semantic, Phonemes.*

Language is a mere symbol of conventional vocal signs through which human beings communicate. Change is inevitable, so is in the case of language. Languages change with time and it is history that records language change. The change can be at any level of structure phonological, morphological, syntax, semantics and lexical. In day-to-day communication, such changes may not be evident as they are gradual. But however languages change, flourish, expand and some even come to the verge of extinction. It is the borrowing and invention of new words and evolving of pronunciations from generation to generation which leads to language change.

While addressing language change there arises various questions like why and how languages change. To explain why a language change is difficult for which historical linguists study how languages change or evolve from time to time. There

is not even a single language without change. All languages change. But in some cases, the rate of change may considerably vary due to certain factors. It is continuous and regular. Eventually, there can be large scale changes to a language with time where the early version of the language becomes unrecognizable.

Articulatory simplification can be another factor of language change. Traditionally it was related to the idea of ease of articulation. In day-to-day conversation, there are many instances of articulatory simplification where speakers delete consonant sounds or insert vowel sounds in a complex structure. For example Assimilation is another kind of ease of articulation where one sound influences the pronunciation of the adjacent sound. For instance, vowels before nasal consonants are often nasalized due to assimilation. Change within language has humble beginnings often involving a choice in pronunciation between two words. Spelling pronunciation can be another factor of language change. While pronouncing a word, the written form can be significantly different from that of the spoken one. For example- the word 'often' [ɔftən]. Earlier speakers pronounced it with the /t/ sound. But subsequently, the voiceless stop was lost which resulted in a pronunciation like [ɔfən] and reintroduced as the pronunciation of the word. There are also cognitive factors that can result in language change. One among which is an analogy. It is the preference of the speakers for the regular patterns over irregular ones. For instance, the regular past tense marker is -ed. In words like dance/danced, play/played, examine/examined, the -ed marker is used to mark the past tense of the words. But due to analogy speakers are saying as She waked last night (instead of 'woke'), He lighted the candles (instead of lit). Another example of analogic change is exceptional plural forms. There are certain borrowed irregular plural forms such as datum/data, curriculum/curricula, agendum/agenda and memorandum/memoranda to mention a few. But speakers have replaced these

irregular plural forms with the regular ones such as curriculums, agendas and memorandums considering words such as agenda to be in plural form. Language contact can be another factor in language change. When a speaker of one language continuously interacts with the speakers of another language, such a situation is referred to as language contact. This leads to extensive borrowing which affects all components of grammar especially the lexicon is mostly affected. A few examples of words borrowed from other languages are-

- Flour, Juice, Pantry- Old French
- Sugar- Arabic
- Tea- Dutch
- Coffee- Turkish
- Tomato- Spanish
- Ketchup- Malay

Political factors also play an important role in language change. Due to migration and invasion, when people migrate from one country to another they learn a new language with little imperfection and then pass it to their children. This might alter the language. Increasing environmental awareness and gender-neutral languages have led to the coinage of phrases like 'eco-friendly', 'go green', 'eco-terrorism' etc. Gender equality gave rise to certain genderneutral words like humankind (instead of mankind), the owner (instead of landlord), the police officer (instead of policeman) and workforce (instead of manpower). Social changes can also be a factor in language change. In every society, people are living with different social status variables which include occupation, income and education level who chose to use language and vocabulary differently. There are certain factors like the speaker's gender and age that can also influence language change.

It is the morphology that acts as the mediator between syntactic case and

surface realization. It is a history that records the change in the construction of grammar. Language change is observable in morphological aspects also. For instance, the use of the third person gender marker in Old English was different for marking Masculine, feminine and neuter gender. But at present time the demonstrative pronoun ‘that’ is used regardless of any gender. Similarly in Modern English ‘you’ is used to refer to both singular and plural forms while in Old English the word ‘thou’ was used to address one person and ‘ye’ was used to refer to more than one person.

Language is considered as a marker of ethnic identity which brings attachment among the people of the same social group. In contemporary times, according to old folks language change is perceived as a negative thing. While younger generations are considered to be carriers of language change. Speakers of a language need to be accommodative of changes because without change there can be barriers among the language in communication. It is through language people communicate with speakers of other tradition and culture. So, changes can enrich the vocabulary of a language unless too many changes do not let the speakers lose their linguistic identity.

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